

Human Resource Career Development Practices and Retention of Secondary Schools' Teachers in Rubabo County, Rukungiri District, Uganda

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between human resource career development practices and retention of teachers in secondary schools in Rubabo County, Rukungiri District, Uganda. The objectives of the study were to establish the relationship between employee performance appraisal, staff training practices, promotion practices and retention of teachers in secondary schools in Rubabo County Rukungiri District. The study adopted the correlational research design on a sample of 153 using a self-administered questionnaire. Data were analysed using quantitative data analysis methods namely; descriptive statistics that were frequencies, percentages and means, and inferential analyses that were correlation and regression analyses. Descriptive analysis revealed that

teacher retention, performance appraisal, training practice and promotion were moderate. Regression analysis revealed that training had a positive and significant influence on the retention of teachers but employee performance appraisal and promotion practices had a positive but insignificant influence on the retention of teachers. Therefore, it was concluded that training was a pre-requisite for promotion retention of teachers. However, employee performance appraisal and promotion in the schools were weak to influence the retention of workers. It was thus recommended that the government of Uganda and schools' authorities provide teachers with opportunities for training. Still, the Education Service Commission, headteachers and foundation bodies which are responsible for the promotion of teachers should reform the promotional practices in order to provide higher chances of promotion since promotion was almost non-existent. In addition, school headteachers should implement an effective performance appraisal system because it was low in schools.

Key words: Career Development, Employee performance appraisal, Promotion, Retention, Training.

Introduction

Retention of teachers has been a major concern in educational research and policy analysis because of the challenges turnover creates in the attempt to replace those that leave (Sindelar, McCray & Brownell, 2014). Retention of teachers is very important for schools because retaining teachers of high quality that are qualified enables schools to provide high-quality education. Turnover and turnover intentions of teachers in schools have a negative impact on student satisfaction and their educational development (Tehseen & UIHadi, 2015). Teacher turnover harms student learning, institutional memory is lost and resources are wasted on the hiring process (Ronfeldt, 2013). Teacher attrition is costly both for a nation's budget and for the social and academic outcomes of its citizens (Mason & Matas, 2015). The education sector of Uganda

has not been spared from the consequences of teacher attrition because of teacher retention challenges. This is because the country has been experiencing turnover of teachers as a result of resignation, dismissal and pre-mature transfers in different schools. The turnover rate in the teaching profession has been consistently higher than in many other occupations in the country. This factor has led to the inability of the education sector to maintain high-quality teachers in the classroom (Ministry of Education and Sports, 2013).

While in the past especially during the 1990s national teacher turnover rates were as high as about 22-23% annually (Boe, Cook & Sunderland 2008), the 2000-2001 teacher follow-up Survey revealed that attrition rates had increased by 50% (Luekens, Lyter & Fox., 2004). According to the Ministry of Education and Sports sector annual performance report for financial year 2013/2014, over 12700 teachers were leaving public service for greener pastures annually (Kagolo, 2014). To avert attrition of teachers and promote their retention, the Ministry of Education and Sports, headteachers, parents and Board of Governors put in place measures such as improving teachers' working conditions by providing them meals, accommodation and increasing their pay. Despite these interventions, teacher retention remained low. While limited studies have such as Jingdong, Najjuko and Ochwo (2017) and Muhangi (2017) have been carried out on retention of teachers or its related concepts of turnover or turnover intention in Uganda, none related it with career development. This study, therefore, examined the relationship between human resource career development practices and retention of teachers in secondary schools in Uganda.

Describing the Conceptual Background

Retention of Teachers

Retention of teachers can be defined as the process of physically keeping teachers in a school for the maximum period of time (Aguenza & Som, 2018). Therefore, in a school teacher retention is a technique adopted by the school management to maintain an effective workforce of teachers while still meeting operational requirements. Management of a school takes systematic effort to create and foster an environment that encourages teachers to remain employed by establishing policies and practices in place that address their diverse needs (Kossivi, Xu & Kalgora, 2016). Retaining key employees such as high-quality teachers is a vital source of competitive advantage for school institutions (Aguenza & Som, 2018). Retaining teachers in schools helps in improving the learning of students which has a positive effect on the students

(Bland, Church & Luo, 2014). Teacher retention in schools leads to positive school environments and good student outcomes. Also, teacher retention is likely to spur good school performance and lead to higher student achievement and result in productive behaviours amongst students (Adnot, Dee, Katz & Wyckoff, 2017). Retaining high-quality teachers is a challenge with regions most susceptible to shortages of quality teachers being large cities and rural areas. This is because in many urban areas the cost of living is higher yet teachers can do other jobs. Teachers in urban areas quit teaching because of low expected earnings in teaching relative to earnings in other professions. In rural areas, it is difficult to attract high-quality teachers because of location and available resources (Bland et al., 2014). Rubabo County in Rukungiri District in Uganda being a rural area, this study sought to establish the level of retention of teachers and factors that underpinned it looking at career development.

Human Resource Career Development Practices

Career development involves the management of a person's growth and progress in his or her career (Gyansah & Guantai, 2018). Career development is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future (Higgs, Crisp & Letts, 2019). Career development is a lifetime process that encompasses the growth and change process of childhood, the formal career education at school, and the maturational processes that continue throughout a person's working adulthood and into retirement (Tüzünkan & Altintas, 2018). Therefore, human resource career development practices refer to a set of systematic and planned activities designed by an organisation to provide its members with the opportunities to learn necessary skills to meet current and future job demands (Tizikara & Mugizi, 2017). Mugizi (2019) operationalised human resource career development practices in terms of performance appraisal, training and promotion.

Performance appraisal refers to the systematic evaluation of the employee with regard to his or her performance on the job and his potential for development (Mugizi & Bakkabulindi, 2018). Performance appraisal provides a major potential for employee feedback that links strongly to increasing motivation, an opportunity to clarify goals and achieve long-term individual performance and career development (Mugizi, Bakkabulindi & Bisaso, 2015) which most likely might result into employee retention. Training is a systematic approach to learning and development to improve the individual, team and organisational effectiveness (Buckley, Wheeler & Halbesleben, 2017). Training builds employee capabilities increasing feelings of internal control

(autonomy) and competence (Mugizi, 2019) which in turn may lead to employee retention. Promotion refers to an increase in job responsibility, scope, authority, or level within or outside the organisation (Mugizi & Bakkabulindi, 2018). Promotions are important to the employee because of the benefits from promotions including monetary gains and higher reputation (Mugizi et al., 2015) that may attract an employee to want to stay on the job. Empirically, this study analysed how the three concepts of performance appraisal, training and promotion related to employee retention.

Theoretical Framework

The Perceived Organisational Support Theory (POS) by Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchinson and Sowa (1986) explained this study. POS postulates that employees develop global beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values their contribution and cares about their well-being (Satardien, Jano & Mahembe, 2019). Employees perceive their organisation as supportive when they are rewarded beyond their contractual agreements (Boateng, 2014). POS holds that in order to meet socio-emotional needs and to assess the benefits of increased work effort, employees form a general perception concerning the extent to which the organisation values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Giorgi, Dubin & Perez, 2016).

That is, when employees feel that they are supported by the organisation, they reciprocate it with an increased level of job satisfaction, commitment, better performance and high work efforts. A sense of reciprocity is created when employees feel that they are supported by the organisation (Giorgi, Dubin & Perez 2016). Therefore, if the employer grants employees support in terms of appropriate appraisal, training and promotion, among others, they will reciprocate with positive attitude towards work such as the desire to stay on the job or retention (Nasurdin, Hemd & Guat, 2008). POS proposes that supportive human resource career development practices such as performance appraisal, training and promotion might enhance job performance. Therefore, POS Theory was the basis for relating human resource career development practices and retention of teachers

Literature Review

Employee Performance Appraisal and Retention of Teachers

Different scholars (e.g. Al Damoe & Hamid, 2017; Beulen, 2009; Fahim, 2018; Thite & Russell, 2010) related performance appraisal and retention of employees. For instance, Al Damoe and Hamid (2017) examined the direct effect of HRM practices on staff retention in the context of

Libyan organisations. The findings indicated that performance appraisal had a significant impact on staff retention. Beulen (2009) examined the contribution of a global service provider's human resources information system to staff retention in emerging markets using Accenture's HR executives and managers in Argentina, Brazil, China, India, Latvia and Slovakia. Interview data revealed that performance appraisal contributed to the retention of employees. Fahim (2018) in a study on strategic human resource management (SHRM) practices in the public sector used staff of National Bank of Egypt. The findings revealed that there was a positive significant relationship between performance appraisal and employee retention. Thite and Russell (2010) examined specific aspects of HR practice including performance appraisal for their effect on retention on staff of Indian call centres. The findings revealed HR practices were a necessary but not sufficient condition for retention workers. However, as the studies above suggest, they were all done outside Uganda and none in a secondary school. Still, the study by Thite and Russell (2010) revealed controversial results indicating that HR practices including performance appraisal were not a sufficient condition for retention workers. These gaps made it necessary for this study to further test the relationship between performance appraisal and retention.

Training and Retention of Teachers

Scholars (Abba, 2018; Fletcher, Alfes & Robinson, 2018; Ma, Mayfield & Mayfield, 2018; Pandita & Ray, 2018; Vui-Yee, 2018) have studied the relationship between training and retention of workers. For example, Abba (2018) examined the relationship between training and employee retention in some selected banks within Bauchi metropolis. Using regression analysis, the findings showed that training had a positive relationship with employee retention. Bibi, Ahmad and Majid (2018) investigated the impact of training on employees' retention using faculty members working in public sector universities in Pakistan. The study revealed that training had a significant relationship with the retention of employees. Fletcher et al. (2018) examined the relationship between perceived training and development and intention to stay using employees across organisations in the United Kingdom. The findings showed that the association between perceived training and intention to stay was not significant.

On their part, Ma et al. (2018) carried out a critical review of literature on how organisations can develop employee embeddedness to increase employee retention. The review revealed that companies can increase employee fit through training leading to employee retention. Companies can enhance fit by offering training that aligns individual to organisational goals.

Pandita and Ray (2018) carried out a meta-analysis on the impact of talent management engagement on talent retention. The findings suggested that training in terms of providing employees learning initiatives, coaching and mentoring related to employee retention. Vui-Yee (2018) analysed the relationship between training and employee turnover intention with employees public and private organisations in Malaysia as a unit of analysis. The results predicted that training had no direct effect on turnover intention hence predicted employee retention. While the literature above shows that scholars have made significant effort to relate training to the retention of employees, none of the studies was done in the context of an organisation in Uganda. Still, Fletcher et al. (2018) contradicted the findings of other scholars by indicating that the relationship between training and retention was not significant. These gaps, therefore, made it imperative in the context of Uganda for this empirical study to analyse the relationship between training and employee retention.

Promotion and Retention of Teachers

A number of scholars (e.g. Chew & Chan, 2008; George, 2013; Ma et al., 2018; Huang, Lin & Chuang, 2006; Moncarz, Zhao & Kay, 2009) have related promotion to retention of employees. For instance, Chew and Chan (2008) examined the impact of key human resource (HR) practices on permanent employees' intention to stay from large public and private Australian organisations that included health care, higher education, public sector and manufacturing. The findings indicated that intention to stay was significantly related to career development or promotion. George (2013) investigated why professional workers actually remained in their organisations in cross-sectional workers in a multinational Marketing company in the United Kingdom. The findings indicated that promotion prospects were an important feature for employee retention. Ma et al. (2018) in a critical review of literature revealed that companies can increase employee fit through promotion leading to employee retention.

Accordingly, offering employees promotion opportunities that aligned to organisational goals led to employee retention. Huang et al. (2006) examined the effect of individual-based, firm-based and market factors on job retention with employees who left their jobs at one firm and human resource managers and those who left for other jobs in China. The results showed that the speed of promotion had a significant impact on how long the employees retained their jobs. Moncarz et al. (2009) examined the impact of employee-retention initiatives and practices on employee turnover and retention using senior-level executives of lodging management companies in the US.

The findings revealed that promotional practices influenced non-management employee retention. Nevertheless, while all the studies revealed that there was a relationship between promotion and employee retention, all the studies were skewed towards outside Uganda. Therefore, it was considered essential to further test the relationship between promotion and employee retention in the context of Uganda.

Methodology

Sample and procedure

A sample of 147 teachers that included subject teachers, class teachers and head of departments provided data. The teachers from government-aided secondary schools in Rubabo County in Rukungiri District in southwestern Uganda. The study was a correlational study with quantitative data collected using a questionnaire survey. The sample was selected using simple random sampling. The teachers that provided data were selected from a sampling frame giving each individual teacher in the population the opportunity to participate in the study. The sample was chosen to provide data because being active teachers, they could easily give their perceptions about the human resource career development practices implemented in the schools and how they influenced their desire to stay in the schools. The researchers personally collected data and observed research ethics throughout the whole process of collecting data. The researchers thus sought informed consent from the respondents, ensured anonymity and confidentiality during data collection, respected the privacy of the respondents and reported data with honesty by ensuring that data presentation, analysis and interpretation were strictly based on the data collected.

Instrumentation

Since the study used the quantitative approach which in particular was the survey design, data were collected using a Self-Administered Questionnaire (SAQ). The SAQ was adopted from previous studies and validated to fit in this study. This was based on the premise that validities and reliabilities of the SAQ items could be taken for granted initially. The SAQ was divided into three sections that were A through C. The question items in section A were nominal questions on demographic characteristics. Section B and C question items were ordinal questions on the dependent variable (retention of teachers) and independent variable (human resource career development practices). Retention of teachers was studied as unidimensional concept with items ($\alpha = 0.91$) adopted from Kyndt, Dochy, Michielsens and Moeyaert (2009). Human resource career development practices covered three constructs that were performance appraisal, training and

promotion. The items for performance appraisal were 10 items, that were six items ($\alpha = 0.894$) from Mugizi and Bakkabulindi (2018) and four items ($\alpha = 0.86$) from Tziner, Latham, Price and Haccoun (1996). The items for training were 11 ($\alpha = 0.915$) obtained from Truitt (2011). Promotion was studied with five items (5 items, $\alpha = 0.874$) adopted from Mugizi and Bakkabulindi (2018). The five-point Likert scale (where 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = undecided, 2 = disagree, 1 = strongly disagree) was adopted for the questions in sections B and C.

Data Management and Analysis

Data collected were processed by coding the questionnaires used in collecting data, entering the data into the computer using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), summarising the data using frequency tables and editing them to remove errors. The reliabilities for the items in the different constructs were attained at $\alpha = 0.60$ above. Factor Analysis and Cronbach's alpha tests were done to confirm the validity and reliability of the data. Data analysis was at univariate, bivariate and multivariate levels. At the univariate level, data were analysed using descriptive statistics specifically "means". At the bivariate level, the dependent variable (DV), retention of teachers was correlated on human resource career development practices, namely; appraisal, training and promotion the independent variables (IVs). At multivariate level, the DV was regressed on human resource career development practices (IVs) using multiple regression. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to carry out data analysis.

Results and Findings

Demographic Characteristics

The findings in Table 1 on demographic characteristics of the teachers indicated that the model percentage (65.1%) was of males, aged 30-39 years (49.7%), possessed diplomas (55.0%), had experience of less than 5 years (57.2%) and were subject teachers (44.2%).

Table 1: Background Characteristics

Item	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	97	65.1
	Female	52	34.9
	Total	149	100.0
Age groups in years	Up to 29 years	37	24.8
	30-39 years	74	49.7
	40-49 years	28	18.8
	50 years and above	10	6.7
	Total	149	100.0
	Diploma	82	55.0

Highest level of education	Bachelor's Degree	67	45.0
	Total	149	100.0
Working experience	Less than 5 years	83	57.2
	5-10 years	51	35.2
	11 years and above	11	7.6
	Total	145	100.0
Responsibility held in school	Subject Teacher	65	44.2
	Class Teacher	39	26.5
	Head of Department	39	26.5
	Senior Administrator	4	2.7
	Total	147	100.0

Retention of Teachers. Retention of teachers (RT) was analysed as a unidimensional concept using 11 items. The results on retention of teachers included frequencies, percentages and means. The results also included validity and reliability test results in the form of factor loadings and Cronbach's alphas (α) respectively. Factor loadings and Cronbach's alphas explained the accuracy and interrelatedness of the items measuring the concept of retention of teachers. The results on retention of were as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Means, Factors Loadings and Cronbach's Alphas on Components for Retention of Teachers

Retention (RT)	Means (\bar{x}) (Overall \bar{x} =2.95)	1	2	3	4	Alpha (α)
RT1	2.69	0.786				0.632
RT2	2.99	0.752				
RT3	3.23	0.737				
RT4	3.54	0.628				
RT5	2.56		0.747			
RT6	2.21		0.689			
RT7	2.99		0.668			
RT8	3.60			0.793		
RT9	3.23			0.735		
RT10	2.99				0.821	
RT11	2.47				0.599	
Eigenvalue		3.215	1.579	1.355	1.186	
% variance		29.229	14.359	12.316	10.783	

The results in Table 2 show that the retention of teachers (RT) was rated as being moderate (mean = 2.95 corresponding to undecided). Factor Analysis showed that the component of retention of teachers could be condensed to four factors, with eigenvalues of 3.215, 1.579, 1.355 and 1.186. Put together, the factors explained over 66% of the joint variation in the respective items constituting the factor. With a factor loading of at least 0.5 considered strong (Yong & Pearce, 2013), Table 2 suggests that all the items loaded highly on the corresponding factors. The

Cronbach's alpha obtained for the construct of retention of teachers of 0.632 was deemed sufficient as Ursachi, Horodnic and Zait (2015) indicate that the generally accepted rule is that α of 0.6-0.7 indicates an acceptable level of reliability. Therefore, the items measuring the retention of teachers were reliable measures.

Human Resource Career Development Practices

Human resource career development practices were studied in terms of performance appraisal (PA), training (TP) and promotion practices (PP). The results for the three constructs included frequencies, percentages and means. For each human resource career development practices, factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha (α) results were presented showing the validity and reliability of the results. The results in Table 3 shows that teachers rated human resource career development practices (overall mean of PA = 2.93, TR = 3.25 & PP = 2.94 all corresponding to undecided) as being fair or moderate. Factor Analysis suggested that the items for performance appraisal could be condensed to only two factors, with the factors having eigenvalues of 34.570 and 1.634. The two factors explained over 45% and 16% of the joint variation in the respective items constituting performance appraisal. Items for training could be condensed to only three factors with the factors having eigenvalues of 3.705, 1.492 and 1.410. The three factors explained over 33%, 13% and 12% of the joint variation in the respective items constituting training.

Items for promotion could be condensed to only two factors with the factors having eigenvalues of 4.570 and 1.634. The factors explained over 45% and 16% respectively of the joint variation in the respective items constituting the factor of promotion. Considering a factor loading of at least 0.5 strong, Table 3 suggests that each item loaded highly on the corresponding factor. Therefore, all the items were valid measures of the respective human resource career development practices (performance appraisal, training and promotion). The Cronbach's alphas = 0.863, 0.790 and 0.813 for the respective components of human resource career development practices were above the acceptable level = 0.6-0.7. This suggests that the items for the three practices were reliable measures.

Table 3: Means, Factors Loadings and Cronbach's Alphas for Human resource career development practices

Performance appraisal (PA)	Means (\bar{x}) (Overall \bar{x} =2.93)	Factors Loadings		Alpha (α)	
		1	2		
PA1	3.03	0.801		0.863	
PA2	3.01	0.792			
PA3	2.67	0.786			
PA4	3.03	0.761			
PA5	3.24	0.723			
PA6	3.52	0.679			
PA7	2.94	0.603			
PA8	2.80		0.876		
PA9	2.48		0.824		
PA10	2.62		0.706		
Eigenvalue		4.570	1.634		
% variance		45.698	16.344		
Training (TR)	Means (\bar{x}) (Overall \bar{x} =3.25)	Factors Loadings			Alpha (α)
		1	2	3	
TR1	3.46	0.844			0.790
TR2	3.57	0.809			
TR3	2.94	0.804			
TR4	3.03	0.706			
TR5	2.78		0.813		
TR6	3.05		0.618		
TR7	3.04		0.615		
TR8	2.44		0.562		
TR9	3.70			0.771	
TR10	3.92			0.675	
TR11	3.81			0.643	
Eigenvalue		3.705	1.492	1.410	
% variance		33.686	13.566	12.820	
Promotional Practices (PR)	Means (\bar{x}) (Overall \bar{x} =2.94)	Factors Loadings		Alpha (α)	
		1	2		
PP1	2.89	0.903		0.813	
PP2	2.81	0.807			
PP3	2.30	0.805			
PP4	3.39		0.916		
PP5	3.32		0.913		
Eigenvalue		4.570	1.634		
% variance		45.698	16.344		

Human Resource Career Development Practices and Retention of Teachers

Preliminary analysis to establish the relationship between human resource career development practices and retention of teachers involved carrying out a correlation analysis. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation between Human Resource Career Development Practices and Retention of Teachers

	Retention of Teachers	Performance Appraisal	Training Practices	Promotional Practices
Retention of Teachers	1			
Performance Appraisal	0.334**	0.000		
Training Practices	0.370**	0.491**	1	
Promotional Practices	0.290**	0.352**	0.545**	1
	0.001	0.000	0.000	

The results in Table 4 suggest that all the three human resource career development practices had a positive and significant relationship with retention of teachers. However, while the relationship between performance appraisal ($r = 0.334$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and training ($r = 0.599$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) with retention of teachers was moderately positive and significant, the relationship between promotional practices ($r = 0.290$, $p = 0.001 < 0.005$) and retention of teachers was weakly positive and significant. The preliminary analysis suggested that training correlated more with retention of teachers followed performance appraisal and promotional practices respectively.

Table 5: Regression of Retention of Teachers on Human Resource Career Development Practices

Human Resource Career Development Practices	Standardised Coefficients Beta (β)	Significance p
Employee Performance Appraisal	0.129	0.218
Training Practices	0.298	0.009
Promotional Practices	0.105	0.338

Adjusted $R^2 = 0.177$
 $F = 8.577$, $p = 0.000$

a. Dependent Variable: Retention of Teachers

The results in Table 5 show that the three human resource career development practices namely; performance appraisal, training and promotional practices explained 17.7% of the variation in retention of teachers (adjusted $R^2 = 0.409$). This means that 82.3% was accounted for

by other variables not considered in this model. The regression model was significant ($F = 8.577$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). However, of the three factors, training ($\beta = 0.298$, $p = 0.009 < 0.05$) had a positive significant influence on retention of teachers. Performance appraisal ($\beta = 0.129$, $p = 0.218 > 0.05$) and promotional practices ($\beta = 0.105$, $p = 0.338 > 0.05$) had a positive but insignificant influence on retention of teachers. Nevertheless, the magnitudes of the respective betas even showed that the relationship between training and retention of teachers was weak.

Discussion

The results showed that retention of teachers in the schools was low. This finding was consistent with the premise on which this study was based that retention of teachers in Uganda was low. For instance, Kagolo (2014) had reported that the Ministry of Education and Sports sector annual performance report for financial year 2013/2014 revealed that over 12700 teachers were leaving public service. The findings further revealed that performance appraisal had an insignificant influence on the retention of teachers. This finding was consistent with the finding by Thite and Russell (2010) that performance appraisal was not a sufficient condition for retention workers. However, the finding was inconsistent with the findings of most scholars. For example, Al Damoe and Hamid (2017) reported that performance appraisal had a significant impact on staff retention. Similarly, Beulen (2009) revealed that performance appraisal contributed to retention of employees. Further still, Fahim (2018) reported that there was a positive significant relationship between performance appraisal and employee retention. With the finding of the study inconsistent with the findings of most scholars, it can be deduced that the performance appraisal system in the schools studied had a limited influence on the retention of teachers.

Nonetheless, the results revealed that training had a positive and significant influence on the performance of teachers. This finding concurred with Abba (2018), and Bibi et al. (2018) who reported that training had a positive relationship with employee retention. Also, Ma et al. (2018) expounded that companies can enhance fit by offering training that aligns the individual to organisational goals. Relatedly, Pandita and Ray (2018) reported that training in terms of providing employees learning initiatives, coaching and mentoring related to employee retention. Similarly, reporting in the converse, Vui-Yee (2018) reported that training had no direct effect on turnover intention. However, on the contrary, Fletcher et al. (2018) established that the association between perceived training and intention to stay was not significant. Nevertheless, with the finding of the

study concurring with the findings of previous scholars, it can be affirmed training influence retention of teachers.

With respect to promotional practices, the results showed that the relationship with retention of teachers was insignificant. This finding disagreed with the findings of previous scholars. For instance, Chew and Chan (2008) reported that the intention to stay was significantly related to career development. Likewise, George (2013) indicated promotion prospects were an important feature for employee retention. Ma et al. (2018) explained that offering employees' promotion opportunities that aligned to organisational goals led to employee retention. Also, Huang et al. (2006) revealed that the speed of promotion had a significant impact on how long the employees retained their jobs. Lastly, Moncarz et al. (2009) reported that promotional practices influenced non-management employee retention. With the finding of the study disagreeing with the findings of all the previous, it was inferred that the promotional practices in the schools in Uganda were poor to motivate retention of teachers.

Conclusions

The discussion above led to the conclusion that performance appraisal and promotion of teachers in the schools were weak to influence their retention. This was because, in the schools, appraisers gave limited feedback to teachers about their performance, teachers were not regularly appraised, appraisal did not significantly advance careers of teachers and appraisal was not fair. With the promotion, the challenge was that there were limited opportunities for teachers to get promoted, the promotional opportunities available were not very satisfying and the promotion policy was not very clear to teachers. Also, promotion was not largely based on merit and teachers did not have a clear understanding of the promotion requirements. However, training was observed to a pre-requisite for retention of teachers. This was because teachers received positive feedback on how they should carry out their jobs, were guided on how to carry out certain activities, were availed training opportunities and were encouraged to participate in seminars and workshops. In addition, teachers attended refresher courses, had instructional manuals on job performance, had the opportunity to go for further studies, were delegated responsibilities and superiors provided them instructions on activities to accomplish.

Recommendations

It was recommended that school headteachers should implement an effective performance appraisal system. The appraisal system should ensure that appraisers give feedback to teachers about their performance, appraisal is regular, advance careers of teachers and appraisal is fair. Also, the government and schools' authorities provide teachers with opportunities for training. The training should involve teachers being instructed to carrying out their jobs, having training opportunities and participating in seminars and workshops. Teachers should also attend refresher courses, have instructional manuals, and opportunities to go for further studies, be delegated responsibilities and be given instructions on activities to accomplish. Lastly, the Education Service Commission, headteachers and foundation bodies which are responsible for the promotion of teachers should reform the promotional practices in order to provide higher chances of promotion since promotions were almost non-existent. Still, the promotional opportunities need to follow a clear policy that is satisfying to teachers and based on merit.

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APPENDIX

Study Instrument

Construct	Item	Measures
Section A: Background Characteristics (BV)		
	BV1	Gender (Male, Female)
	BV2	Age groups in years (Up to 29 years, 30-39 years, 40-39 years, 50 years and above)
	BV3	Highest level of education attained by the respondent (Diploma, Bachelor's degree, Post graduate qualifications)
	BV4	Experience (Less than 5 years, 5 - 10 years, 11 years and above)
	BV5	Responsibility (Subject Teacher only, Class teacher, Head of Department, Senior administrator)
Section B: Retention of Teachers (RT)		
	RT1	The conditions provided by this school are that even if I were start over again, I would still choose to work for this school
	RT2	I would wish to stay in this school for much of my teaching career life
	RT3	The work I am doing this school is very important to me than if I was in another school
	RT4	If I wanted to do another job or function, I would look first at the possibilities within this school
	RT5	Trying to look for a job in a school that might be better than this rarely crosses my mind
	RT6	The conditions in this school are appealing that even if I received an attractive job offer from another school, I would remain in this school
	RT7	The management of this school has made me love working for it
	RT8	It does not matter if I am working for this school or another, as long as I have work
	RT9	I have been making an attempts to move to another school that is better than this one.
	RT10	I am guaranteed to work for this school in the next three years as long as I still want.

	RT11	Management has put arrangements that if I want, I can definitely work for this school for a longer time
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Section: Human Resource Career Development Practices		Measures
Performance Appraisal (PA)	PA1	In this school after every appraisal I receive feedback about my performance
	PA2	The appraisal system of this school has a strong influence on my performance
	PA3	In this school I am appraised at regular intervals
	PA4	The appraisal system of this school advances my career
	PA5	The performance appraisal system of this school is fair
	PA6	In this school my performance is measured on the basis of objective results
	PA7	Supervisors give performance ratings that please those they appraise
	PA8	Supervisors rate subordinates in a way that will make them like the supervisors
	PA9	Supervisors' performance ratings reflect in part their personal liking or disliking individual teachers
	PA10	Supervisors give appraisal ratings to depending on the relationship they have with those they appraise
Training (TR)	TR1	My supervisors provide me positive feedback on how I should carry out my job
	TR2	I have been guided on how to carry out certain activities by my superiors in this school
	TR3	This school has availed training opportunities on use of new technologies in teaching
	TR4	In this school I have been encouraged to participate in seminars and workshops I have
	TR5	I have been offered an opportunity to attend a refresher course
	TR6	I have been provided with manuals with job performance instruction in this school
	TR7	I have been provided with the opportunity to go for further studies
	TR8	I have been taken on a visit to learn from a better performing school
	TR9	The position I hold in this school has many responsibilities to accomplish
	TR10	I have acted in different responsibilities in this school
	TR11	My superiors provide me instructions on activities to accomplish
Promotion Practices (PP)	PP1	There is an opportunity for me to get promoted in this school soon
	PP2	The promotional opportunities available to me in this school are satisfying
	PP3	Management of this School has communicated the promotion policy to me very clearly
	PP4	Promotion in this school is based on merit
	PP5	I have a clear understanding of the promotion requirements of my job in this school